

A REVIEW PAPER ON STUDY OF ROAD USER CHARACTERISTICS USING VISSIM FOR INDIAN SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

With rising levels of urbanization and vehicle traffic, India's transportation scene is changing quickly. In this dynamic context, an understanding of road user characteristics is essential for efficient transportation planning and traffic management. This study analyses road user behaviour and features in the Indian environment using VISSIM, a microscopic traffic simulation program. The study's primary objective is to gather actual traffic data from India's urban and suburban areas, including a range of factors such as user behaviour, traffic density, and road conditions. The study examines variables such as vehicle speeds, acceleration patterns, lane-changing behaviour, and interactions with other road users like cyclists and pedestrians using VISSIM models. Important conclusions from the research provide insight into the particular difficulties and traits faced by Indian drivers, such as the impact of cultural norms, infrastructure constraints, and legal frameworks on driving habits. Additionally, the study pinpoints possible areas for enhancing safety precautions, traffic flow, and urban mobility planning specific to the Indian context. The findings of this research enable in the creation of more precise traffic models and simulations for Indian cities, which in turn helps transportation engineers, urban planners, and policymakers create effective and sustainable transportation networks. The knowledge gained can also be used to guide the creation of focused actions and policies meant to improve traffic safety and lessen congestion in India's transportation system.

Keywords: Road User Characteristics, VISSIM, Traffic Simulation

Cite this Article: Sahana Upadhye and Nikhil T R, A Review Paper on Study of Road User Characteristics Using VISSIM for Indian Scenario, Journal of Public Transportation System (JPTS), 3(2), 2024, 23-39.
<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/JPTS?Volume=3&Issue=2>

1. INTRODUCTION

India has seen tremendous economic expansion and urbanization in recent years, along with a notable rise in vehicle traffic. The increase in demand for transportation has highlighted a number of issues with road user behaviour, traffic control, and infrastructure development. To effectively handle these issues and guarantee safe and effective transportation within Indian cities, it is vital to comprehend the traits and behaviours of road users. Using simulation tools such as VISSIM to examine road user characteristics provides an invaluable way to understand and analyse the intricacies of traffic behaviour in the Indian setting. With the use of a microscopic traffic simulation program called VISSIM, individual cars and their interactions within a fictitious road network may be precisely modelled. Researchers can learn more about variables including car speeds, lane-changing patterns, and interactions with cyclists and pedestrians, among other things, by utilizing VISSIM. Using VISSIM as an analytical tool, this project seeks to advance knowledge of road user behaviour in Indian cities. Through the collection of actual data from various urban and suburban regions around India, the study aims to identify traffic dynamics patterns and trends that are unique to the Indian context. The project aims to determine important elements influencing road user behaviour and its consequences for transportation planning and management using microscopic simulations.

The necessity of examining road user characteristics in the Indian setting and the function of simulation technologies like VISSIM in enabling such research are outlined in the study's introduction, which also sets the scene. It also emphasizes how important this research is to solving the problems of traffic congestion, road safety, and urban mobility in Indian cities. This project intends to provide evidence-based policies and interventions targeted at developing safer, more sustainable, and efficient transportation systems for India's changing urban landscape by exploring the subtleties of road user behaviour.

2. CRITICAL REVIEW ON STUDY OF ROAD USER CHARACTERISTICS

Given are some of the most important reviews of the literature on road user characteristics that have been published on national and international magazines.

The way drivers behave at the intersection under study presents significant risks, including lengthy lines and delays at intersection approaches, particularly in the morning and evening when traffic is at its highest. Through an assessment of intersection performance in relation to the existing traffic conditions in Ilorin city, this study examined the performance of traffic at a specific intersection. Drone cameras were used to gather traffic data at the Maraba Intersection in Ilorin City because they offer a permanent record of data with the least amount of labour. Manual counting was used to retrieve the data, which were then processed using Excel sheets. To simulate the current traffic situation, a virtual environment was created using the VISSIM micro-simulation model. The average approach delays from the field research and the VISSIM simulation model were evaluated, and it was found that there are no major disparities between the field and model data, with the percentage difference between the two being less than 10%. [1]

For the purpose of designing, analysing, operating, and managing road facilities, a thorough understanding and study of traffic stream characteristics is required. This research aims to analyse the features of the traffic stream and model the traffic flow using the four-lane divided Mahatma Gandhi highway connecting Ahmedabad and Vadodara. The chosen road segments are simple sections of an expressway situated in an undeveloped area. There are several categories for vehicles: Light Commercial Vehicle (LCV), Bus, Truck, Big Car, and Small Car. The video graphic approach is used to collect traffic data. Video files have been manually processed to obtain data on various vehicle categories' speeds, traffic volume, composition, lane usage, etc. According to the data, when traffic is moving freely, over 97% of cars are staying in their designated lanes. The findings indicate parabolic connections between flow-density and speed-flow in addition to different speed-density relationships. The expressway's capacity is determined to be roughly 4377 PCE/hour/direction for a traffic stream with roughly 25% heavy vehicles.[2]

The safety and health consequences of the risk homeostasis theory. The research makes the case that until a certain speed is achieved, drivers seek to maintain a level of task complexity, with sentiments of danger being closely related to task difficulty but not to ratings of statistical risk. The paper's TCI model, which emphasizes task difficulty homeostasis and a dynamic control-motivational framework, offers a paradigm for comprehending driver behaviour based on the relationship between task demand and driver competence. Task complexity It is suggested that maintaining homeostasis is a crucial sub-goal in driving, and that choosing one's speed is the main way to address the issue of keeping task difficulty within predetermined bounds. It is made clear how task complexity, mental effort, and calibration relate to each other.[3]

A system for traffic simulation based on agents that allows for intelligent virtual driver behaviour. Using ideas from Artificial Life (ALife), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Agent technology, the framework simulates drivers' innate unpredictable and autonomous behaviour in traffic simulation models. With this method, part of the prescriptiveness of driving simulation models is replaced because behaviours are allowed to arise from the interactions between individual driver agents. By enhancing existing restrictions that focus accident investigation techniques on the events themselves rather than precrash variables, the framework also advances accident analysis. Using ideas from artificial life, artificial intelligence, and agent technology, the methodology entails creating an agent-based traffic simulation framework, creating driver agents with knowledge and decision-making capabilities, and putting the framework into practice using C++ programming and UML notation.[4]

Predictive models of the driver's interaction with the car and surroundings are required in order to forecast how different assistance technologies will affect the driving behaviour of the driver. The study highlights the significance of comprehending why drivers behave as they do in various circumstances and examines the two approaches to modelling driver behaviour: functional models and descriptive models. It draws attention to how important driver assistance technologies, such as collision warnings, are to improving driving habits and performance for increased safety. The primary goal is to simulate how different independent variables affect how drivers receive information and react to emergencies while taking into account the function of in-car driver assistance technologies.[5]

The majority of current driver behaviour models (DBMs) are created for the overall driving population in particular scenarios, including changing lanes or following another car. As a result, there are insufficient DBMs that capture individual behaviour in diverse contexts.

This research uses risk thresholds that capture the time headway and time to line crossing to propose a novel approach of quantifying individual perceived driving danger in both longitudinal and horizontal directions. These are combined in a risk-based DBM that is developed using the model predictive control (MPC) paradigm while accounting for the dynamics of the vehicle. According to the DBM, drivers function as predictive controllers that collaborate to optimize a variety of factors, such as trip inefficiencies, discomfort, and driving danger. Using the dynamic bicycle model to predict ego vehicle dynamics, integrating risk thresholds for individual perceived driving risk in the longitudinal and lateral directions, developing a risk-based driver behaviour model within an MPC framework, and accounting for driving risk, discomfort, and travel inefficiency are all part of the methodology. The study focuses on developing assumptions about driver behaviour based on predictive and optimal/switching controllers and comprehending driving behaviour at the operational level.[6]

An essential component of intelligent transportation systems, driver identification technology permits the creation and use of customized in-car features while preventing unauthorized use. The system works with accelerator and brake pedal signals, so it may complement any existing technologies, such as microphones or cameras. Furthermore, the approach works with cars that can only use conventional sensing modalities. We test the framework using 15 hours of driving data totalling 416 km driven, which includes GPS traces from four separate drivers traveling the same route and messages from an electric vehicle's CAN bus. We get an identification rate accuracy of more than 95%. [7]

A framework for simulating driver behaviour within driving simulators is described in this paper. Fuzzy Logic is used in the methodology to handle imprecision and uncertainty in the development of a four-unit framework (Perception, Emotions, Decision-making, and Decision-implementation) that models human-like driving behaviours for autonomous vehicles in driving simulators. The framework, which consists of four parts that provide flexibility in constructing multiple driver behaviour models, is presented in the study as a means of modelling human-like driving behaviours for autonomous vehicles in driving simulators. Planning decisions are handled by a traffic controller that runs scripts. The current model can only replicate how people might drive in a rural, two-lane setting. [8]

Subsequent driving aids will be engineered so that their functions mesh with the driver's perception and motor control loops without causing any adverse disruption. Without incorporating a model that enables reliable driver behaviour predictions into the design process, this goal cannot be accomplished. Within that framework, the understanding and modelling of the driver's steering behaviour will be covered in this study, with a focus on the function of visual cues and kinaesthetic feedback. This essay explains the driver's speed management and steering techniques and analyses the combined cornering and braking situation. In order to determine anticipatory speed control during curve negotiation, the driver's visual direction information is utilized for speed control. The approach entails describing steering and speed control techniques, modelling the driver's steering behaviour with a focus on visual cues and kinaesthetic feedback, and putting forth a structured model of the human driver that takes internal driver behaviour mechanisms into account. The paper presents a method to control vehicle speed when approaching curves and suggests an organized model of the human driver that takes into account different sensory inputs. [9]

A novel driver behaviour model that mimics distinct driving behaviours—that is, driving styles—for diverse driver classifications. Built on a two-layer Hierarchical Concurrent State Machines (HCSM) programming framework, the model was extremely parametric.

Our study is especially designed to provide a realistic urban traffic scenario with real-life hazardous circumstances in a driving simulator, allowing inexperienced drivers to practice in a secure setting. The TRAFIKENT driving simulator served as a test-bed for our investigation. Tests and analyses produced satisfying findings about our model's behavioural validity.[10]

Driving schools are incorporating driving simulators into their curriculum more and more, although there are still questions about the tools' apparent usefulness, particularly in terms of preventing accidents.

In order to shed light on the efficacy of this training approach, we look into the variables that are associated with driving accidents in virtual training. The two things we choose to take into account are: 1) the excessive speed, and 2) the breach of the safety distance. The inability to anticipate the actions of other drivers and the often felt "feeling of presence" that affects performance in virtual tasks are the other two issues. Our study, which included 36 participants, found no statistically significant link between any of these variables and the quantity of automobile accidents that occurred during the virtual driving task. Using driving simulators, 36 people participated in the study, which examined issues such as speeding, failing to maintain a safe distance, being unable to predict the behaviour of other drivers, and the sensation of being there. Automated data collection methods included accident and infraction data as well as participant perception and behaviour data gathered through questionnaires. A number of statistical analysis, such as Spearman correlations, were performed to investigate any relationships between the variables and the quantity of accidents.[11]

A vehicle platoon is a collection of vehicles that use vehicle automation and vehicle-to-vehicle communication to drive together at a consistent speed with little inter-vehicle spacing. Platoon-oriented cut-in experiments are used in the paper's methodology to gather driver data under various conditions. Later, the MPC method is used to develop lateral and longitudinal control models, which are then implemented in the QN architecture. Parameters are then tuned based on experimental data, and driving performance is assessed using a variety of metrics. The subjects were told to perform cut-ins approaching a platoon as they would in real-world driving settings. The studies were carried out in a laboratory setting with a virtual scenario and a simulated vehicle.[12]

Realism in crisis management training environments necessitates precise simulation of driver behaviour during evacuations. More specifically, the most sophisticated traffic simulators on the market today do not account for the interdependence of driver behaviours that are regularly seen in real-world evacuations. To address this problem, we propose an agent-based behaviour model based on the social forces model of crowds. We use utility-based path trees in our model to describe the aspects that a driver considers when making decisions. By using a metric of route similarity, we demonstrate that our model can mimic the evacuation behaviour of drivers who follow other people's routes in real life.

The model is tested on three distinct road networks: the artificial "ladder" network, the road networks in Louisiana, the United States, and Southampton, the United Kingdom. The two most common route selection algorithms, quickest route and real-time re-routing, are compared against the model. Using our route choice forces model increases our route similarity measure by 21%–93%. A qualitative comparison further demonstrates that the model can mimic behavioural patterns observed during the 2005 Hurricane Katrina evacuation of the New Orleans area.[13]

The identification of the parameter set that requires adjustment is the fundamental and necessary element in the calibration process of the microscopic traffic simulation model. The intersections of Ronghua Road and Wing King Street and the Shangdi Roundabout are chosen for this paper's experiments, and the evaluation index is based on travel time and wait length.

Next, it uses Vissim, a microscopic traffic simulation program, to do a sensitivity analysis of the calibrated parameters. It makes use of range analysis, line chart technique, and sensitivity coefficients to do a comparative assessment of the evaluation outcomes. Lastly, there are differences between the sensitivity criteria of an intersection and a roundabout. Specific roundabouts and crossings were selected as evaluation indices, queue length and travel duration were picked, and sensitivity analysis was performed using range analysis, line chart approach, and sensitivity coefficients.[14]

Efficient vehicle traffic modelling is still a contentious topic, especially given the variety of driving conditions in India. India is getting more and more accustomed to VISSIM, a program that mimics microscopic traffic. However, changes need to be made to the basic behavioural settings in order to effectively simulate the various traffic circumstances found in India. This study proposes a method and conclusions on automatic VISSIM model calibration and sensitivity analysis using data from a junction in Chennai. Large traffic use this crossing during peak hours. Sensitivity analysis was employed to determine the VISSIM factors that impact driving behaviour in India's diverse environments. ANOVA and the elementary effects approach were used for the sensitivity analysis. The model was calibrated using the Visual C++ COM interface provided by VISSIM. A genetic algorithm was used to select the optimal set of sensitive parameters during calibration.[15]

A rigorous method of using journey time estimates from a limited number of Bluetooth detectors to calibrate Vissim's motorway network. Professionals that want to build road networks using microscopic simulation technologies might utilize the case study that was generated as a model. We will analyse a three-hour microscopic traffic simulation model that simulates a motorway network located in the greater region of Bavaria, Germany. The network has 500 links, 113 nodes, and 1820 origin-destination pairs. When the model is systematically calibrated and validated following the suggested methods, it produces very good results in 96.5% of the produced intervals for both cars and heavy vehicles.[16]

The current work provides a method for using vehicle trajectory data gathered in mixed traffic scenarios without lane separation to calibrate the vehicle-following behaviour in VISSIM. Two access-controlled mid-block parts are identified, one on a multi-lane urban road with a six-lane divided carriageway and the other with an eight-lane divided carriageway, in order to acquire high-quality vehicle trajectory data in this environment. Later, lane-wise time-space plots were made using trajectory data for the cars' simultaneous movement from neighbouring lanes as well as within the same lane in order to analyse non-lane-based movement. The investigation is carried out by using leader-follower vehicle relationships (hysteresis plots) between relative distance and relative velocity for vehicles in the same lane as well as other surrounding lanes. The process consists of three steps: Psychophysical vehicle-following model calibration, leader-follower vehicle detection, and VISSIM 8.0 simulation.[17]

The simulation experiment was conducted for all-cars traffic and varying traffic compositions on an eight-lane divided multi-lane urban road in Delhi, India. The existing compliance level on a selected multilane urban road in Delhi is determined to be approximately 40%. The article emphasizes the importance of driver compliance for safety and investigates the impact of driver compliance levels with posted speed limits on roadway capacity and critical speed. The study highlights the potential advantages of high driver compliance with speed limits by indicating that non-complying vehicles are not significantly slowed down compared to complying vehicles since there is a lack of lane-based behaviour in Indian traffic conditions. The methodology entails developing distinct speed distribution patterns for vehicles that comply with and do not comply with speed limits, conducting simulation experiments under various scenarios with drivers at varying compliance levels, and obtaining desired speed parameters through field measurements.[18]

Due to a lack of lane discipline and varied traffic, traffic in developing nations has unique characteristics. This causes the driving habits of these nations to diverge from those of industrialized nations. Given that most driver models are designed by analysing drivers from wealthy nations, it is not surprising that simulations run with these models do not match field data from underdeveloped countries. The study highlights the difficulties associated with driving in developing nations and urges further investigation into risky driving practices and disregard for local traffic laws. In order to find important questions on driving behaviour in developing nations, the methodology comprised doing a systematic literature review (SLR) using specific databases, refined keywords, a stop criterion, and the goal question measure (GQM).[19]

Different vehicle types' manoeuvrability translates into driving habits that are reliant on the type of vehicle used for both longitudinal and lateral movement. The study highlights the necessity for sophisticated models that can faithfully capture the intricate interactions and behaviours seen in real-world scenarios as it explores the difficulties and approaches involved in modelling driver behaviour in mixed traffic situations. Unique driving behaviours in mixed traffic include tailgating, swerving, and filtering, whereby drivers create their own virtual lanes. A review of data extraction techniques, traffic data needs, and Hossain and McDonald's continuous lateral movement model suggestion are all part of the process. Later, a semi-discrete solution utilizing virtual lanes for vehicle tracking is added to the mix.[20]

When there is non-lane-based heterogeneous traffic flow, one of the most important factors to take into account for safe traffic maneuverability is the conduct of the drivers of the vehicles. The assessment of multilane highway capacity using a microscopic simulation model that takes driver behaviour into account is covered in the study. The findings provide realistic capacity estimation that is in line with Indian Highway Capacity Manual values. The approach comprised estimating the capacity of multilane roadways under Indian settings using a microscopic simulation model. Selecting study portions, gathering data by video graphic techniques, analysing the data for volume, density, composition, and speed distribution of traffic, and using the data as input parameters for capacity calculation and simulation preparation were all part of the process.[21]

Negative downstream conditions, such as lengthy lines and haphazardly placed traffic signals, might encourage drivers' need for a speedy discharge in locations with high traffic demand and closely spaced junctions. This can result in a reduced saturation flow rate (SFR) for upstream lane groups. Although it acknowledges the constraints of ignoring some influencing elements, the research presents an updated intelligent driver model to estimate the reduction in saturation flow rate (SFR) while taking downstream conditions into account. The model shows a strong fit to actual data. The methodology entails creating a better intelligent driver model, using MATLAB to simulate a process, gathering empirical data using a video survey, and calibrating the model to make it optimal. The limitations of leaving some parameters out of the analysis are also acknowledged in the paper.[22]

Despite a great deal of progress in the study of car-following behaviour, there is currently no car-following model that takes into account all driver, vehicle, and environment characteristics. In order to close this gap, the literature on car-following behaviour research that took the driver, vehicle, or environment into account was reviewed. The contributions and shortcomings of earlier studies were also examined, and this paper addressed the prospects and needs for further exploration. The technique entails a review of prior studies on car-following behaviour with an emphasis on driver-vehicle-environment relationships. It also discusses the shortcomings of these studies and the potential for further research. It highlights the value of trajectory data and the possibility of combining data-driven and theory-driven models.[23]

In the automobile industry, advanced driver assistance systems, or ADASs, are currently receiving a lot of attention since they provide improvements in comfort, safety, and vehicle energy usage. The goal of the study is to aid the selection of acceptable solutions in the field of Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADASs) by providing a thorough evaluation of Model Predictive Controls applied to ADASs. The paper focuses on the effectiveness of these controls in improving vehicle energy efficiency, safety, and comfort. To assess the effectiveness of MPC-based ADAS controllers, the process entails database analysis, section organization on MPC strategy, numerical and experimental analysis, and testing in diverse conditions.[24]

Various research traditions in psychology have endeavoured to elucidate individual variations in risky driving behaviour and involvement in traffic accidents. The current study aims to comprehend the mechanisms behind adolescent drivers' risk-taking behaviour in traffic by integrating two of these research traditions: the personality trait approach and the social cognition method. A questionnaire survey was used as part of the technique to gather information on personality traits, risk perception, attitudes, and self-reported dangerous driving behaviours from 1932 teenagers in Norway. Structural equation modelling was used to analyse the connection between the variables and Cronbach's alpha was used to assess internal consistency.[25]

When there is traffic congestion on a non-signalized freeway, there are several tell-tale signs, such as crashes involving cars, ramps, sudden braking, inclement weather, etc. Sometimes, though, traffic congestion on the road occurs for no apparent reason. The accumulation of delays caused by individual drivers' perception and response times causes congestion. It's known as the "stop and go effect." It is known that the driver's aberrant conduct or incorrect geometric design is the true source of this ailment. The advances in connected vehicle (CV) technologies, the value of improved radio communication technology, the contribution of CV environments to traffic volume reduction under appropriate conditions, the importance of the market penetration rate of CV environment vehicles, and the application of MOEs to road condition assessment are all covered in this paper. Additionally, it makes recommendations for ways to lessen traffic volume and boost the market penetration rate of CV environment vehicles in order to alleviate traffic congestion.[26]

Through the use of variable speed limit (VSL) systems, which modify speed restrictions based on actual traffic conditions, road conditions are improved. In order to enhance traffic conditions during accidents, the usage of Variable Speed Limit (VSL) systems is discussed in the article. It also evaluates the usefulness of VSL systems in a connected car environment and highlights how affordable they are for managing traffic events.

The methodology entails putting forth and assessing a VSL system in a connected vehicle environment, assessing traffic efficiency, safety, and environmental impact through microscopic traffic simulation, and structuring the paper into sections that address the theoretical framework, experimental design, findings, conclusions, and next steps.[27]

The goal of the development of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) is to enhance the energy-saving, safety, and efficiency of transportation networks. The most popular of these services is the Variable Speed restriction (VSL) system, which modifies the speed restriction on the road in reaction to traffic, incidents, and/or meteorological conditions. The Variable Speed Limit (VSL) system's use and efficacy in enhancing road efficiency and lowering fuel consumption in a Naples highway segment are discussed in this study. The results demonstrate favourable effects on traffic flow, average speed, speed variance, and environmental footprint. The methodology entailed evaluating the impact of a reactive rule-based VSL system on a Naples freeway segment through numerical simulations carried out with the VISSIM microscopic traffic simulator.

The goal of the project was to assess the benefits of mobility and the environment by dynamically modifying the speed limits on the roads in response to data gathered from loop detectors regarding volume, occupancy, and average speed.[28]

In a driving simulator, a 10 mi² (25 km²) network was created, and it was subsequently exported to a traffic simulator. Approximately thirty participants operated the simulator with and without integration, subjected to varying traffic and driving circumstances, and variable message sign (VMS) data. By combining driving and traffic simulators, the study investigates how drivers behave in response to changeable message signs. It discovers that variables such as exposure, route advice, and VMS information affect drivers' choices and diversion of routes. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining a traffic simulator and a driving simulator, analysing route diversion causes using binary logistic regression, and examining route choice behaviour using multinomial logistic regression. The individuals were also given route suggestions.[29]

Access-controlled mid-block sections of multi-lane urban roadways in the cities of Delhi and Chennai are taken into account. With the potential to be applicable to Asian nations with non-lane-based traffic flow scenarios, the paper assesses vehicle following behaviour under heterogeneous traffic conditions using trajectory data, calibrates Wiedemann car-following models, validates the models, and suggests updating guidelines by the Indian Roads Congress. The methodology focuses on leader-follower pairs and heterogeneous traffic situations and includes data gathering, time-space plot building, calibration of following behaviour, and simulation model development.[30]

With the use of the Vissim model, driving behaviour characteristics were altered to create a virtual environment that mimicked a traffic scenario. This helped to optimize the problem and visualize the necessary solution to address present challenges and make improvements for the future. There is now a performance metric in place. Identification was made possible by differentiating between the next set of uncontrollable input parameters, which included traffic counts, current signal timing plans, and existing geometry, and the controllable input parameters, which included minimum and maximum look ahead distance, waiting time before diffusion, lane changing distance, and minimum headway. Using Vissim parameters, several parameters were tested during the calibration process.[31]

An important factor in a nation's socioeconomic development is its transportation infrastructure. The use of microscopic simulation models in the planning, optimisation, and assessment of the sustainability of transportation networks and related management approaches is growing. In the realm of traffic simulation, VISSIM, a microscopic traffic simulation program, has quickly become well-known. It was discovered that the default values for a number of sensitive parameters, including lane change distances, additive and multiplicative portions of desired safety distances, the number of vehicles spotted before, amber signal decisions, and minimum headway, were the most sensitive and crucial parameters to be calibrated in order to accurately replicate field conditions. The simulation findings with default variables produced longer queue lengths, quicker link speeds, and shorter trip durations as compared to field observations. However, there was similarity between the measures of effectiveness (MOEs) obtained from calibrated models over targeted simulation runs and field surveys. Within a 5–10% range, all validation MOEs of the model matched the field-observed values.[32]

VISSIM, a microscopic traffic simulation model, has been used frequently to assess the operational effectiveness of traffic networks. It has also been used more frequently lately for safety evaluation.

However, modelers are effectively left in the dark about how VISSIM's parameter values for car-following and lane-changing models affect the safety of simulated vehicles (aggressiveness or defensiveness) and how they interact with the operational aspect of the simulated traffic. This work provides a quantitative evaluation of these parameters' influence on a total of 21 VISSIM driver behaviour parameters (10 for car-following and 11 for lane-changing models) using sensitivity analysis. It is found that parameter values have a substantial impact on the degree of aggression or defensiveness displayed by the simulated cars, which in turn impacts the safety and operations of the simulated traffic.[33]

There are numerous methods available for evaluating roundabout performances (capacity, service levels, etc.), including as statistical models (TRRL, SETRA), analytical models (HCM, HBS, etc.), and more. Different roundabout aspects (vehicle traffic, geometric parameters, and behavioural concerns) are taken into account by each technique. The results obtained are often non-comparable due to the distinct properties of each technique. At present, the most efficient way to address this problem is to use advanced vehicular circulation simulation software. The authors of this study describe the findings of an extensive survey conducted on a variety of roundabout scenarios using the simulation tool VISSIM. The traffic flow characteristics (dynamic traffic assignment, approach speed, circulatory speed, reduced speed zones, etc.); behavioural features (priority rules, minimum gap, minimum headway, etc.); and geometric elements (inscribed circle radius, circulatory roadway, central and splitter islands, etc.) are used in each scenario to describe a fixed roundabout phenomenon. The results of the stop-line delay analysis are displayed.[34]

A sensitivity analysis of the VISSIM simulation capacity result for a variety of driver behaviour parameter factors. A simulation designed for the George Bush Turnpike (US-75 and SH-190) interchange north of Dallas, Texas, is the purpose of the research. Every driver behaviour attribute, including look-back distance, has its simulated capacity changed as the exact value is changed. Until each parameter's examination is complete, all other parameters—aside from the one under investigation—remain at their calibrated values. The purpose of this paper is to assist practitioners who are developing and fine-tuning VISSIM simulation models in understanding the various driver behaviour elements and how adjusting them can impact the model's performance. Furthermore, this effort is intended to lay the groundwork for the possible development of a quantitative, optimization-based calibration method for the VISSIM driver behaviour characteristics.[35]

With an emphasis on traffic calming solutions, the purpose of this article is to examine driving behaviour in order to build a strategy for optimizing micro- and macrosimulation traffic models. As a result, volume-delay functions were attempted to be estimated, speed profiles were computed, and a PTV Vissim model was produced. Based on video recordings of traffic in traffic-calmed links, driver behaviour was simulated. To be used in Vissim, speed distributions were computed and speed profiles were split between sections where traffic calming had an impact on speed and those where it did not. To determine the relationship between traffic flow and trip time, Vissim microsimulation was done with varying traffic volumes and traffic compositions.[36]

In VISSIM, a model was constructed and calibrated using information gathered from video recordings. The study identifies factors that are important for modelling driving behaviour and the challenges that come with calibrating the model realistically with video observations and model-specific constraints.

It was found from the camera records that the main source of the congestion was the mainline traffic that was using the on-ramp. To solve this issue, two merging control techniques were proposed: the installation of a canter barrier and sequential merging areas.

The outcomes demonstrated that both strategies can lessen individual travel times while also improving the traffic condition. The most effective solution was to install a canter barrier, which cut travel times by 16.58% on the mainline and 63.24% at the on-ramp.[37]

Microsimulation, or software for microscopic simulation, is a useful analytical tool that provides an efficient and affordable analysis of real-world traffic scenarios. Careful calibration is necessary to keep microsimulation models reliable, accurate, and predictive. Determining the roadway's capacity is a crucial step in the calibrating process. Microsimulators such as VISSIM, which have user-defined input parameters, regulate the capacity of roadways. Previous studies have shown that capacity is impacted by every highway driver behaviour variable found in the VISSIM model. This study looks at the relationships between pairs of driver behaviour characteristics and the capacity of the roadway. Four interactive correlations were identified and investigated for this investigation of the dynamic relationship between driver behaviour and simulated capacity. Learning more about these relationships will be beneficial for developing automatic calibration methods as well as for manually calibrating VISSIM microsimulation models.[38]

The goal of the current research project was to examine intercity traffic flow characteristics. It was discovered throughout the project that the data might not be entirely sufficient to establish Measure of Effectiveness (MOE) levels. Consequently, the traffic flow on particular study parts is being modelled using a simulation-based approach. This served as the basis for calibrating the simulation model, VISSIM-9.0, utilizing a recently created technique for mixed traffic situations. Specifically, premium vehicle trajectories were used to calibrate driving behaviour characteristics. The US-HCM (2010) criteria are reasonably matched with the capacity value of approximately 7500 PCU/h/direction for a six-lane split expressway with three lanes in each direction. It is expected that the suggested approach, which uses high-quality trajectory data to calibrate vehicle-following driving behaviour, can be applied to other mixed traffic scenarios.[39]

The current study demonstrates that in scenarios with mixed traffic flow, the capacity of a multilane roadway may be computed using VISSIM software. The speed-flow curve is created using traffic flow data from the four-lane divided highway stretch. Using the same set of field data, VISSIM compares the simulated speed-flow curve with the field curve. It was found that the initial design of VISSIM overestimates the capacity and speed of the route. The results of determining the driver behaviour parameters CC0 and CC1 under homogeneous traffic conditions—conditions in which only one of the four automobile categories in the stream is present—are combined to determine the values of these parameters for mixed traffic streams. On a different four-lane divided highway length with paved shoulders, where the field capacity was 5277 pcu/hr and the simulated capacity was 5329 pcu/hr, the technique is shown to work.[40]

DOTs are using more and more traffic simulation technologies for a range of traffic study studies, including evaluating the effects of work zone traffic. This is partly because of their capacity to assess the traffic performance by modelling every vehicle and driver behaviour at an incredibly comprehensive level. By modifying the driving behaviour parameters, the simulation models must be calibrated to match the field conditions (such as lane capacity and queue lengths) in order to be used accurately for traffic analysis of construction zones. The estimated statistical models can provide a variety of parameter values that result in a broad range of capacities that are utilized by US state DOTs. Field data from Ohio work zone sites is also used for model validation. The validation results demonstrated the ability of the model's suggested settings to generate precise capacity and queue length estimations.[41]

The Wiedemann vehicle-following model uses thresholds to define several car following regimes. Certain thresholds only consider the difference in speed between the lead and subject cars, whereas others incorporate a speed component as well. The results show that the thresholds are not constant, but rather vary over a range of speeds. Notable is also the apparent driver-dependent variance in the speeds. The results imply that drivers act differently depending on the speed, which could mean that animosity rises to particular speeds.[42]

Since traffic safety is a global concern, designing safety study procedures that yield trustworthy results and, eventually, suitable preventive actions, requires an interdisciplinary scientific approach. It can be difficult to distinguish between harmful and appropriate behaviour. Due to their rarity and difficulty in identifying reasons, raw accident data is insufficient and does not include ex-ante evaluations. Scholars continue to disagree about the use of traffic safety indicators and their cut-off values. The article describes a variety of methods for assessing driver behaviour and objective behavioural indicators that are commonly used as traffic safety measures, including time to collision, post-encroachment time, deceleration rate, time headway, red-light violations, lane deviations, gap acceptance, and others. The aim of this paper is to provide a comprehensive framework for examining reliable and valid criteria in traffic safety research.[43]

The ability of PTV VISSIM software to accurately simulate traffic at a circular crossroads in Silchar, Assam. Software called VISSIM simulates tiny traffic and aids in producing a realistic image of the diverse field circumstances. Traffic volume, cumulative vehicle arrivals and departures, and traffic data from the intersection have all been gathered by the software. The software's provided volume is contrasted with the field set of values. Both CC0 and CC1 driving parameter calibrations have been completed. The standstill distance (CC0) in meters and the time headway (CC1) in seconds were adjusted until the simulated and real worlds closely matched each other.[44]

The identification of the parameter set that requires adjustment is the fundamental and necessary element in the calibration process of the microscopic traffic simulation model. The intersections of Ronghua Road and Wing King Street and the Shangdi Roundabout are chosen for this paper's experiments, and the evaluation index is based on travel time and wait length. Next, it uses Vissim, a microscopic traffic simulation program, to do a sensitivity analysis of the calibrated parameters. Sensitivity coefficients, range analysis, and line chart approach are used to do a comparison examination of the valuation outcomes. Lastly, there are differences between the sensitivity criteria of an intersection and a roundabout.[45]

How to create and calibrate an accurate VISSIM freeway model is demonstrated on a 15-mile stretch of I-210 West close to Pasadena, California. This test location poses a number of challenges for microscopic modelling, including an intermittent barrier in an HOV lane, a major highway junction, twenty metered onramps with and without HOV bypass lanes, and three interlocking bottlenecks. The field data fed into the model came from a manual assessment of the onramps and offramps as well as loop-detectors on the onramps and mainline (PeMS). Owing to gaps in both sources, it was necessary to use a composite data set consisting of several average days. The following procedures were followed in order to construct the model: 1) identifying the most important geometric features; 2) collecting and evaluating traffic information; 3) examining mainline data to identify recurring bottlenecks; 4) utilizing VISSIM coding; and 5) calibrating the model using the findings from the third stage. A collection of qualitative goals was created for the calibration. To satisfy this, very small adjustments were made to the driver behaviour parameters (CC-parameters) in VISSIM.[46]

For transportation authorities, a crucial stage in the work zone planning and scheduling process is the traffic effect assessment. Transportation authorities can perform in-depth studies of work zone mobility performance measures during the planning and scheduling phase thanks to microscopic traffic simulation models. The flow and speed at the work zone taper and at the road segments upstream of the work zone are replicated by the driver behaviour parameters. A framework for particle swarm optimization is suggested in order to increase the calibration process's effectiveness. It was discovered that the ideal time headway for large vehicles was 2.31 seconds, whereas for passenger automobiles it was 1.53 seconds. It was discovered that the longitudinal following barrier was 11.70 meters for passenger automobiles and 17.64 meters for large vehicles. Field data that hadn't been used to calibrate driver behaviour models before was used to test the suggested values. For the flow rate at the taper, the mean absolute error was 54 veh/h/ln, and the average absolute relative error was 10%. [47]

Microscale traffic simulators are not complete without driving behaviour models for lane changes and acceleration, which are used to assess the effectiveness of various traffic management techniques.

The most advanced lane-changing model has a two-level framework: the target lane is chosen latently, or without observation, at the first level, and the acceptance of adjacent gaps in the target lane's direction is modelled at the second level. The study presented in this thesis suggests adding a third level that specifically models the lane change time to the two-level framework for lane changing models. The third level takes into account traffic circumstances in the driver's area that could affect how long lane changes take. The estimated model is used in the MITSU Lab microscopic traffic simulator, and aggregated traffic data is used for model validation. Results from estimation and validation demonstrate the enhanced modelling capabilities made possible by the suggested modification. [48]

Analysing driving behaviour has long been thought to be a key strategy for coming up with ways to boost road service quality, lower traffic crash rates, enhance car designs, and create in-car safety technology. Understanding the impact of individual differences on driving behaviour and traffic flow characteristics was the aim of this study. Initially, drivers were categorized into three groups using a cluster analysis: aggressive, conservative, and moderate. Second, using the experimental data gathered in a driving simulator, the driving behaviour parameters of the three different driver types were calibrated for traffic simulation models. Next, using traffic modelling techniques, the impacts of driving behaviour on traffic flow were examined. The findings indicate that although the flow velocity on the roads with aggressive drivers is higher, the traffic flow stability is lowest. [49]

Two simulation systems, which differ primarily in their modelling theories, will be used to assess the creation and calibration of a toll plaza simulation model. The two models used are VISSIM, a widely used stochastic simulation program, and SHAKER, a deterministic queuing model for cars using toll collection facilities. The advantages of simulation models led to the goal of this thesis, which is to compare the efficacy of two toll modelling programs with comparable goals but different methods and approaches. It is found that both of the simulation models are successful in simulating toll plaza capacity and queuing once the calibration of the two models is finished. It is to be expected that each simulation model has advantages over the others in terms of setup time, analysis reporting time, and usefulness of outcomes. [50]

3. MAJOR FINDING FROM LITERATURE REVIEW

- The framework attempts to increase understanding of accident causation variables, enhances accident analysis by focusing on pre-crash influences, and models driver behaviour.[4]
- The simulator environment was perceived as typical of urban traffic by the majority of participants.[7]
- At intersections, certain parameters have a greater impact on queue length or travel time than others. Examples of these parameters are the average distance between parking spaces, additional parts of the safety distance, numerous parts of the safety distance, and the minimum headway.[11]
- The significance of comprehending the relationship between journey time and traffic flow while creating volume-delay functions in places with heavy traffic.[35]
- The significance of comprehending the relationship between journey time and traffic flow while creating volume-delay functions in places with heavy traffic.[30]
- The study found characteristics that have a significant impact on the safety of simulated vehicles. This highlights the need to balance parameter values in order to enhance network performance without sacrificing safety.[32]
- Calibration is crucial for successful modelling, as evidenced by the considerable differences between field observations and simulation results obtained using default parameters.[41]
- Using trajectory data, the study effectively calibrated Wiedemann car-following models, producing capacity estimations that were more accurate than default models and near the reported field capacities.[43]

4. CONCLUSION

- The behaviour of drivers on Indian roads varies greatly depending on the type of route, the time of day, and the qualities of the driver. Vissim simulations are able to represent this variety and offer insights into the ways in which various situations impact safety and traffic flow.
- In order to determine the ideal values for the parameters governing microscopic driving behaviour, the calibration and validation process is carried out using microscopic simulation models.
- It is possible to identify and calibrate the significant driver behaviour characteristics that affect both operations and safety.
- Vissim simulation results can provide valuable insights for policy recommendations aimed at boosting traffic flow, road safety, and transportation infrastructure in Indian cities. These suggestions can involve modifications to traffic control plans, driver education initiatives, and road design.
- Traffic dynamics heavily depend on the actions made by drivers, including changing lanes, adjusting speeds, and adhering to traffic regulations. Researchers can examine driver decision-making processes and pinpoint the variables influencing these judgments by using Vissim simulations.
- The kind and layout of urban roads, highways, and intersections all have a big influence on how people use the roads. Vissim simulations aid in the comprehension of how infrastructural modifications might lessen traffic and enhance movement.
- In-depth investigation is required to examine other facets of road user behaviour in the Indian setting, including the effects of developing technology (such linked and driverless cars) and the role of socioeconomic variables on travel habits. Researcher, legislator, and industry stakeholder collaboration can propel progress in transportation planning and management.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ibitoye, B.A., Ibrahim, N.A., Adeyemoh, N.A., Kazeem, M.B. and Daudu, M., 2021. Impact of Road Users Behaviour on Intersection Performance using Vissim Micro-Simulation. *Journal of Architecture and Civil Engineering*, 6(7), pp.39-45.
- [2] Jabeena, M., Joshi, G., Arkatkar, S.S. and Ravinder, K., 2014. Study of flow characteristics and traffic stream modelling on indian expressway: a case study of mahatma gandhi expressway. In *Proceedings of the Eastern Asia Society for Transportation Studies* (Vol. 10).
- [3] Fuller, R., 2005. Towards a general theory of driver behaviour. *Accident analysis & prevention*, 37(3), pp.461-472.
- [4] Dumbuya, A.D., Wood, R.L., Gordon, T.J. and Thomas, P., 2002. An agent-based traffic simulation framework to model intelligent virtual driver behaviour.
- [5] Shinar, D. and Oppenheim, I., 2011. Review of models of driver behaviour and development of a unified driver behaviour model for driving in safety critical situations. In *Human Modelling in Assisted Transportation: Models, Tools and Risk Methods* (pp. 215-223). Springer Milan.
- [6] Yuan, Y., Wang, X., Calvert, S., Happee, R. and Wang, M., 2024. A risk-based driver behaviour model. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 18(1), pp.88-100.
- [7] Marchegiani, L. and Posner, I., 2018, November. Long-term driving behaviour modelling for driver identification. In *2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)* (pp. 913-919). IEEE.
- [8] Al-Shihabi, T. and Mourant, R.R., 2001, May. A framework for modelling human-like driving behaviours for autonomous vehicles in driving simulators. In *Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Autonomous agents* (pp. 286-291).
- [9] Sentouh, C., Chevrel, P., Mars, F. and Claveau, F., 2009, August. A human-centred approach of steering control modelling. In *Proc. 21st IAVSD Symp. Dyn. Veh. Roads Tracks* (pp. 1-12).
- [10] Demir, M. and Çavuşoğlu, A., 2012. A new driver behaviour model to create realistic urban traffic environment. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 15(3), pp.289-296.
- [11] Pallamin, N. and Bossard, C., 2016. Presence, behavioural realism and performances in driving simulation. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 49(19), pp.408-413.
- [12] Lu, Y., Wang, B., Huang, L., Zhao, N. and Su, R., 2022. Modelling of driver cut-in behaviour towards a platoon. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 23(12), pp.24636-24648.
- [13] Handford, D. and Rogers, A., 2011, March. Modelling driver interdependent behaviour in agent-based traffic simulations for disaster management. In *Advances on Practical Applications of Agents and Multiagent Systems: 9th International Conference on Practical Applications of Agents and Multiagent Systems* (pp. 163-172). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [14] Liu, W.W., Qin, Y., Dong, H.H. and Yang, Y.F., 2014. Driving behaviour parameter sensitivity analysis based on VISSIM. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 668, pp.1453-1457.
- [15] Siddharth, S.P. and Ramadurai, G., 2013. Calibration of VISSIM for Indian heterogeneous traffic conditions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 104, pp.380-389.
- [16] Karakikes, I., Spangler, M. and Margreiter, M., 2017. Designing a Vissim-Model for a motorway network with systematic calibration on the basis of travel time measurements. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 24, pp.171-179.
- [17] Raju, N., Arkatkar, S. and Joshi, G., 2021. Modelling following behaviour of vehicles using trajectory data under mixed traffic conditions: an Indian viewpoint. *Transportation letters*, 13(9), pp.649-663.
- [18] Kumar, P., Bains, M.S., Bharadwaj, N., Arkatkar, S. and Joshi, G., 2020. Impact assessment of driver speed limit compliance behaviour on macroscopic traffic characteristics under heterogeneous traffic environment. *Transportation letters*, 12(1), pp.54-65.

- [19] Gracian, V.A., Galland, S., Lombard, A., Martinet, T., Gaud, N., Zhao, H. and Yasar, A.U.H., 2024. Behavioural models of drivers in developing countries with an agent-based perspective: a literature review. *Autonomous Intelligent Systems*, 4(1), pp.1-20.
- [20] Munigety, C.R. and Mathew, T.V., 2016. Towards behavioural modelling of drivers in mixed traffic conditions. *Transportation in Developing Economies*, 2, pp.1-20.
- [21] Ghosh, T., Roy, S.K. and Gangopadhyay, S., 2020. Assessment of multilane highway capacity through simulation process by considering the effect of behaviour of driver of a vehicle. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, 101(4), pp.589-596.
- [22] Zhu, H., Nakamura, H. and Alhajyaseen, W., 2020. Modelling the impact of downstream conditions on discharging behaviour of vehicles at signalized intersections using micro-simulation. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 45(5), pp.4187-4202.
- [23] Han, J., Wang, X. and Wang, G., 2022. Modelling the car-following behaviour with consideration of driver, vehicle, and environment factors: A historical review. *Sustainability*, 14(13), p.8179.
- [24] Musa, A., Pipicelli, M., Spano, M., Tufano, F., De Nola, F., Di Blasio, G., Gimelli, A., Misul, D.A. and Toscano, G., 2021. A review of model predictive controls applied to advanced driver-assistance systems. *Energies*, 14(23), p.7974.
- [25] Ulleberg, P. and Rundmo, T., 2003. Personality, attitudes and risk perception as predictors of risky driving behaviour among young drivers. *Safety science*, 41(5), pp.427-443.
- [26] Park, S., Kim, J., Lee, S. and Hwang, K., 2017. Experimental Analysis on control constraints for connected vehicles using Vissim. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 21, pp.269-280.
- [27] Farrag, S., El-Hansali, M.Y., Yasar, A. and Shakshuki, E.M., 2020. Simulation-based evaluation of using variable speed limit in traffic incidents. *Procedia Computer Science*, 175, pp.340-348.
- [28] Di Costanzo, L., Coppola, A., Pariota, L., Petrillo, A., Santini, S. and Bifulco, G.N., 2020, June. Variable speed limits system: A simulation-based case study in the city of naples. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering and 2020 IEEE Industrial and Commercial Power Systems Europe (EEEIC/I&CPS Europe)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [29] Jeihani, M., NarooieNezhad, S. and Kelarestaghi, K.B., 2017. Integration of a driving simulator and a traffic simulator case study: Exploring drivers' behaviour in response to variable message signs. *IATSS research*, 41(4), pp.164-171.
- [30] Raju, N., Kumar, P., Chepuri, A., Arkatkar, S.S. and Joshi, G., 2017. Calibration of vehicle following models using trajectory data under heterogeneous traffic conditions. *96th annual Transportation Research Board, Washington DC*.
- [31] Kumar, P., Bains, M.S., Bharadwaj, N., Arkatkar, S. and Joshi, G., 2020. Impact assessment of driver speed limit compliance behaviour on macroscopic traffic characteristics under heterogeneous traffic environment. *Transportation letters*, 12(1), pp.54-65.
- [32] Al-Ahmadi, H.M., Jamal, A., Reza, I., Assi, K.J. and Ahmed, S.A., 2019. Using microscopic simulation-based analysis to model driving behaviour: a case study of Khobar-Dammam in Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability*, 11(11), p.3018.
- [33] Habtemichael, F. and Picado-Santos, L., 2013, January. Sensitivity analysis of VISSIM driver behaviour parameters on safety of simulated vehicles and their interaction with operations of simulated traffic. In *92nd Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board, Washington, DC* (pp. 1-17).
- [34] Gallelli, V. and Vaiana, R., 2008, May. Roundabout intersections: evaluation of geometric and behavioural features with VISSIM. In *Proceedings of TRB National Roundabout Conference. Kansas City, Missouri, USA*.
- [35] Richter, M. and Paszkowski, J., 2018. Modelling driver behaviour in traffic-calmed areas. *Czasopismo Techniczne*, 2018(Volume 8), pp.111-124.
- [36] Fransson, E., 2018. Driving behaviour modelling and evaluation of merging control strategies- A microscopic simulation study on Sirat Expressway.

- [37] Yannes, C.D. and Lownes, N.E., 2010. Driver behaviour considerations in calibrating microsimulation models for capacity. *International Journal of Society Systems Science*, 2(1), pp.84-99.
- [38] Raju, N., Arkatkar, S. and Joshi, G., 2019. Methodological framework for modelling following behaviour of vehicles under Indian traffic scenario. In *Innovative Research in Transportation Infrastructure: Proceedings of ICHIF 2018* (pp. 1-11). Springer Singapore.
- [39] Mehar, A., Chandra, S. and Velmurugan, S., 2014. Highway capacity through vissim calibrated for mixed traffic conditions. *KSCE journal of Civil Engineering*, 18, pp.639-645.
- [40] Viti, F., Hoogendoorn, S.P., van Zuylen, H.J., Wilmink, I.R. and Van Arend, B., 2010. Microscopic data for analysing driving behaviour at traffic signals. *Traffic data collection and its standardization*, pp.171-191.
- [41] Edara, P. and Chatterjee, I., 2010. Multivariate regression for estimating driving behaviour parameters in work zone simulation to replicate field capacities. *Transportation Letters*, 2(3), pp.175-186.
- [42] Higgs, B., Abbas, M. and Medina, A., 2011, September. Analysis of the Wiedemann car following model over different speeds using naturalistic data. In *Procedia of RSS Conference* (pp. 1-22).
- [43] Niezgodna, M., Kamiński, T. and Kruszewski, M., 2012. Measuring driver behaviour-indicators for traffic safety. *Journal of KONES*, 19, pp.503-511.
- [44] Suresh, A. and Rajbongshi, P., 2016. Traffic Simulation and Calibration of Heterogeneous Traffic by VISSIM. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Technology*, 3(4).
- [45] Liu, W.W., Qin, Y., Dong, H.H. and Yang, Y.F., 2014. Driving behaviour parameter sensitivity analysis based on VISSIM. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 668, pp.1453-1457.
- [46] Gomes, G., May, A. and Horowitz, R., 2004. Calibration of VISSIM for a Congested Freeway.
- [47] Mahmood, B. and Kianfar, J., 2019. Driver behaviour models for heavy vehicles and passenger cars at a work zone. *Sustainability*, 11(21), p.6007.
- [48] Ramanujam, V., 2007. *Lane changing models for arterial traffic* (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology).
- [49] Rong, J., Mao, K. and Ma, J., 2011. Effects of individual differences on driving behaviour and traffic flow characteristics. *Transportation research record*, 2248(1), pp.1-9.
- [50] Russo, C., 2008. The calibration and verification of simulation models for toll plazas.

Citation: Sahana Upadhye and Nikhil T R, A Review Paper on Study of Road User Characteristics Using VISSIM for Indian Scenario, *Journal of Public Transportation System (JPTS)*, 3(2), 2024, 23-39.

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